

SOCIAL ANALYSIS AND ITS SOCIO-ECONOMIC ESSENCE

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ANNOTATION

One of the central issues in project analysis is the human factor. Projects should be focused on modernizing people's lives and improving their standard of living. In the analysis of projects, the interests of the state and the interests of the population are in the first place.

Profit is the first priority in investment projects and business plans of entrepreneurs. The project analysis approach relies on the approach of the Ministry of Industry and Economy and the Ministry of Finance. They evaluate the projects based on the interests of the state and the interests of the population. In this respect, the approach of social analysis and economic analysis in this science is close to each other.

For the effective implementation of any project, the importance of social analysis and the conclusion drawn from this point of view are important.

Key words: *social analysis, economic essence, social essence, investment projects, human factor, demographics*

IJTIMOYIY TAHLIL VA UNING IJTIMOYIY-IQTISODIY MOHIYATI

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ANNOTATSIYA

Loyihalarni tahlil qilishda markaziy masalalardan biri inson omilidir. Loyihalar inson hayotini yengilashtirishga va ularning turmush darajasini oshirishga qaratilishi zarur. Loyihalar tahlilida davlat manfaatlarini va aholining manfaatlarini birinchi o’rinda turadi.

Investitsiya loyihalarida va tadbirkorlarning biznes rejalarida birinchi galda foyda olish turadi. Loyiha tahlilining yondashuvi Sanoat va iqtisodiyot vazirligi va Moliya vazirligining yondashuviga tayanadi. Ular loyihalarga davlat manfaatlarini va aholining manfaatlaridan kelib chiqib baho beradilar va xulosa qiladilar. Shu jihatdan ushbu fandagi ijtimoiy tahlil va iqtisodiy tahlilning yondashuvi bir – biriga yaqindir.

Har qanday loyiha samarali amalga oshirilishi uchun ijtimoiy tahlilning ahamiyati va shu nuqtai nazardan chiqarilgan xulosaning o’rni katta.

***Kalit soʻzlar:** ijtimoiy tahlil, iqtisodiy mohiyati, ijtimoiy mohiyati, investitsiya loyihalari, inson omili, demografiya*

Intorduction

In determining international investment attractiveness, the weight of youth in the population, qualifications of personnel, national customs, demographic characteristics, average life expectancy and many other factors are taken into account.

Failure to fully take into account socio-cultural and demographic characteristics in social analysis has led to the ineffectiveness of projects in the experience of world countries and financial institutions. For example, it is enough to recall the Aswan dam built on the Nile River in Egypt.

The first stage of social analysis is to determine the target population group, its size and composition.

The lifestyle of the target population often differs from the lifestyle of the people developing it. Because of this, if the local population is not involved in the planning process, the project may not fit the local conditions.

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Analysis and results

For projects that affect large numbers of people to be successful, the majority of them must understand and support the project's purpose. Therefore, in the process of developing and implementing projects, it is necessary to take into account the local value system, customs, traditions, identified needs and goals.

Projects that are effective from the point of view of the national economy may be incomprehensible to the local population or, in their opinion, insignificant. As a result, the projects are not supported by the local population. Social analysis shows how to balance project objectives and general goals with the individual goals of local people based on local conditions.

In the case of family planning, the specific characteristics of the local culture also affect the achievement of the project's goal or overall goals shows. Another area where project outcomes depend on people's understanding of the relationship between the project and its benefits is the health sector.

Another condition for the success of the project is to ensure the interest, support and participation of the target group in the project. This is the guarantee of effective operation of the project. People need to be willing to take risks to make a difference and feel confident that their efforts will pay off in order to achieve the project's goals. Project participation can come at all stages and forms, including:

In Uzbekistan, attention is paid at the state level to raise the position of women and girls in the economy and society to a higher level. Therefore, women's issues should always be assessed at all stages of projects.

Often, when discussing projects, it is overlooked that women make up more than half of the world's population. There is a difference between genders in participating in projects and benefiting from them, it is necessary to take into account the economic interests of women in projects, because this is one of the guarantees of the success of the project.

This is especially important in projects of light industrial enterprises, which rely more on the labor of women. Women make up 50 to 80 percent of the world's agricultural workforce. The number of women engaged in agriculture in families is greater than that of men. The length of their working day is the same as that of men.

Summary

From the stage of creation of projects to the stage of effective implementation, its success depends primarily on the level of specialists participating in the project.

Social problems arise at different stages of the project period. The project should be adapted to the customs and traditions of the population not only to prevent negative consequences, but also to mobilize people's energies to initiate social changes. Identifying and getting to the bottom of many social problems allows you to drastically reduce their negative impact on the project.

Professional training and experience in social analysis is essential for identifying potential social problems. Therefore, it is necessary to ensure the participation of specialists such as sociologists and anthropologists in the analysis of the project. Various agriculture in the animal husbandry departments of the institutions, if there are specialists who deal with livestock, those who deal with livestock breeding the lack of specialists is one of the reasons for the low efficiency of livestock projects in many countries.

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